

OncoPharm

Co-funded by
the European Union

**Ministry of education, youth and sports
co-funded by the European Union
Data Management Plan**

8 April 2025

History of changes

Version	Publication date	Changes
v1.3	8 April 2025	Updated repository and standards for naming
v1.2	21 Mar 2025	Updated chapters: instrumental datasets, data formats, type of PID, data access, data availability, other outputs, allocation of resources
v1.1	28 Feb 2025	incorporation of the requirements of the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports
v1.0	21 Feb 2025	transfer DMP to the FAIR Wizard software tool

Contributors

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Projects

We will be working on the following projects and for those are the data and work described in this DMP.

Předaplikační výzkum léčiv pro onkologická onemocnění a pro prevenci a léčbu jimi navozených závažných komplikací

Acronym

OncoPharm

Start date

2024-04-01

End date

2027-09-30

Funding

- **Ministerstvo Školství, Mládeže a Tělovýchovy (Czechia)**
- : CZ.02.01.01/00/23_021/0008442 (granted)

The OncoPharm project focuses on intersectoral research collaboration in the field of cancer pharmacotherapy. Its main objective is to create a knowledge platform for more effective anticancer treatment in terms of minimizing toxicity, overcoming drug resistance and developing new effective anticancer drugs with the aim of personalizing therapy and maximizing therapeutic benefit for the patient. The high degree of interdisciplinarity between the institutions involved will bring the results closer to the needs of real practice.

1. Data Summary

Instrument datasets

The following instrument datasets will be acquired in the project:

- **Datasets will be produced: spectral measurements (UV-vis, fluorescence, NMR, mass), biological data (flow cytometry, PCR, microscope images). However, the published datasets will not contain information from only one instrument, but information from different instruments related to a specific issue.**
- This dataset will be collected by experts in the project, with our own equipment.
- The equipment is very well described and known.
- Other researchers working in the same field of research could be interested in using this data.

Re-used datasets

We have found the following non-reference datasets that we have considered for re-use:

- Data created in our laboratories

There is no need to harmonize different sources of existing data in our case.

Data formats and types

We will be using the following data formats and types:

- **Extensible Markup Language (XML)**
<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.b5cc91>
- It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We will have only a small amount of data stored in this format.
- UV-vis spectra (*.spc, *.dsp), emission spectra (*.fl), IR spectra (*.spa), NMR spectra (fid)
- It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We will have only a small amount of data stored in this format.
- chromatographic records (*.lcd, *.lcm, *.xml), mass spectra and methods (*.datx, *.raw, *.qld, *.ulc, *.ucp, *.spl, *.mdb, *.cdb, *.dat, folders *.M, *.D, *.S)
- It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 2000 GB of data in this format.
- **Joint Photographic Experts Group Format (JPEG Format)**
<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.nggj0j>

- It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 500 GB of data in this format.
- **Crystallographic Information Framework** (CIF)
<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.zr52g5>
- It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We will have only a small amount of data stored in this format.
- **FASTQ Sequence and Sequence Quality Format** (fastq)
<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.r2ts5t>
- It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 200 GB of data in this format.
- **Comma-separated Values** (CSV)
<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.1943d4>
- It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We will have only a small amount of data stored in this format.

Some of them are proprietary formats that are prevalent in the industry. If conversion to a non-proprietary format does not result in a loss of data quality, it will be used.

2. FAIR Data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- **The types of datasets produced in the OncoPharm project will depend on the machines used (see data formats above).**

There won't be different versions of this data over time. We will not be adding a reference to any data catalogue because the data will be stored in a repository that is the prime source of data for re-use in the field.

Provided metadata will follow guideline *Obecné doporučení pro metadatový popis výzkumných výstupů a výzkumných dat* (<https://doi.org/10.48813/yt6w-6h15>).

We will use lab notebooks to make sure that there is good provenance of the data analysis.

The file names will clearly indicate the relationships between the data - this naming key will be provided with the published dataset – this naming key will be provided with the published dataset.

Published datasets will be given a persistent identifier of type: the DOI.

2.2. Making data accessible

We will be working with the philosophy *as open as possible* for our data.

The data cannot become completely open because of:

- legal reasons (data that can lead to the identification patients - mainly data obtained in cooperation with the University Hospital Hradec Kralove)
- patent-related business reasons (data supports patent application)

Data will be released only as soon as restrictions are falling away. Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>) will be used as general repository. If the publisher recommends/requests uploading to other repositories, then other repositories will be used.

Metadata will be openly available including instructions how to get access to the data. Metadata will be available in a form that can be harvested and indexed (managed by the used repository / repositories).

We have a consortium agreement that arranges Intellectual Property.

For our produced data, conditions are as follows:

- **The types of datasets produced in the OncoPharm project will depend on the machines used (see data formats above).**

Where possible, data contained in published datasets will be provided in open formats (as long that this conversion does not compromise the integrity of the data). The datasets will be published after all our processing has finished.

2.3. Making data interoperable

We will be using the following data formats and types:

- **Extensible Markup Language (XML)**
- It is a standardized format.
- UV-vis spectra (*.spc, *.dsp), emission spectra (*.fl), NMR spectra (fid), IR spectra (*.spa)
- It is a standardized format.
- chromatographic records (*.lcd, *.lcm, *.xml), mass spectra and methods (*.datx, *.raw, *.qld, *.ulc, *.ucp, *.spl, *.mdb, *.cdb, *.dat, folders *.M, *.D, *.S)
- It is a standardized format.
- image or video (*.nd2, LIM image, *.jpg, *.tiff, *.avi, *.mp4)
- It is a standardized format.
- crystallography records (*.cif)
- It is a standardized format.
- sequence data (*.fastq), qPCR (*.eds)
- It is a standardized format.
- **Comma-separated Values (CSV)**
- It is a standardized format.

We will use the following standards to increase interoperability:

- **IUPAC Compendium of Chemical Terminology (IUPAC Gold Book)**
(<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.OsiqlF>)
- **Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine, International Version (SNMI)**
(<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.6bxcr4>)

2.4. Increase data re-use

The metadata for our produced data will be kept as follows:

- **The types of datasets produced in the OncoPharm project will depend on the machines used.** – This data set will be kept available until it needs to be deleted for legal, contractual or regulatory reasons. – The metadata will be available even when the data no longer exists.

Datasets will be published under CC-BY 4.0 license. If it is necessary to include supporting information to understand the dataset, it will be published together as a README text file with the dataset. The description of the data processing (e.g. software, methods, instruments)

will be in a publication that will be linked to the dataset. If the dataset itself is published, the data processing will be accompanied by a text document.

As explained in Section 2.2, our data cannot become completely open.

For ethical reasons, we must use anonymization for some data to make it more openly available.

The following procedures in the project will be used for implementation quality processes:

- Calibrating measurements
- Repeat samples / measurements
- Standardized data capture / recording
- Data Entry validation
- Data peer review

To validate the integrity of the results, the following will be done:

- We will be instrumenting the tools into pipelines and workflows using automated tools.
- We will run part of the data set repeatedly to catch unexpected changes in results.

3. Other research outputs

In addition to the datasets, this project will result in publications (published under CC-BY license), functional samples and a patent. Data sharing for the latter two will be in accordance with the requirements of the licensing authorities and it will be necessary to apply a time embargo on access to this information.

4. Allocation of resources

FAIR is a key component of data management planning within the OncoPharm project and is considered in every decision within the data management plan. FAIR processes are utilized to maximize the efficiency of data use.

Costs related to data management during the project are covered by the project budget. The role of the data steward, Jiří Demuth, is funded from the allocated personnel costs of the project. He is responsible for the management and proficiency of data, data policies, data guidelines, and data availability. To execute the data management plan, additional specialist expertise is required and there is such trained support staff available at the institution. Infrastructure and storage costs are supported by institutional resources or included in the project budget in flat rate costs as needed. None of the repositories used require service fees from the project budget.

The costs of ensuring FAIR principles cannot be separated from the rest of the project. A budget has been allocated for data preparation for publication, including planned Open Access fees to ensure accessibility of data. To minimize the one-time burden during publication, most of the work on data accessibility is carried out continuously. No additional hardware or software beyond what is commonly available at the institution is required.

After the project's completion, long-term preservation and access to data will be ensured through data repositories supported by internal funding sources.

5. Data security

Project members will store data or software on computers in the lab. They will not carry data with them (e.g. on laptops, USB sticks, or other external media). Data are stored in local storage infrastructure at each institution. All project web services are addressed via secure HTTP (https://...). Project members have been instructed about both generic and specific risks to the project.

The leaders of the individual research plans/groups will determine access to the data. Therefore, data access will be given to the researchers working on the project and the data steward.

The risk of information loss in the project or organization is acceptably low. The possible impact to the project or organization if information is leaked is small. The risk of information vandalism in the project or organization is acceptably low.

All personal information will be processed in pseudonymized form only. We pseudonymize inside the project, only limited people can access the keys.

The live data will be stored on local servers of the participating institutions. The processed data will be on a local server that is backed up daily. The raw data on the instrumented computers will be backed up regularly to a NAS-type IT storage. Published data will be made available in repositories. Data to be archived will be uploaded to the CESNET data repository. Long-term archiving time depending on the size of datasets to balance benefit vs cost.

We are running the project in a collaboration between different groups and institutes. A collaboration agreement that describes who can have access to what data in the project is set.

6. Ethics

Ethical approvals

The following project require ethical approval:

- **Předaplikační výzkum léčiv pro onkologická onemocnění a pro prevenci a léčbu jimi navozených závažných komplikací (OncoPharm)**
 - case number: *202409 I10P*, status: *granted*

Data we produce

- From the research outputs, it is no longer possible to assign a name to a specific tissue; only general parameters such as age and gender, BMI, etc. are associated with each sample

Data we collect

Informed consent will be required for the creation of datasets based on biological material obtained at the University Hospital Hradec Králové.

We will collect data connected to a person, i.e. "personal data". We explored General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) considerations and relevant materials. We ask the data subjects for their consent. We will collect consent for our use of the data and for anonymization; We will anonymize the data afterwards for reuse. The data subjects will be informed as follows: Informed consent for study inclusion. The consent form will not be available for re-users. The purpose of processing the personal data can be described as follows: The patient will be informed about the possibility of using his/her tissues in research. This familiarisation is taking place at the University Hospital Hradec Králové.

7. Other issues

We use the [FAIR Wizard](https://cuni.fair-wizard.com/wizard) with its *Life Sciences DSW Knowledge Model* (ID: dsw:lifesciences:2.6.8) knowledge model to make our DMP. More specifically, we use the <https://cuni.fair-wizard.com/wizard> FAIR Wizard instance where the project has direct URL: <https://cuni.fair-wizard.com/wizard/projects/efd89de0-a1e5-467a-b58c-c85f6c2668be>.

We will not be using any extra national, funder, sectorial, nor departmental policies or procedures for data management.